

Supporting Table S2

Primers used for cloning described constructs. Restriction sites overhangs in red.

gene	direction	restriction site	Sequence
ARPC2	Forward	<i>Bam</i> HI	GGATCCAATGATACTATTGCAGTCACATTC
	Reverse	<i>Hind</i> III	AAGCTTCTACTTTCGAGTTGGTGTGATTG
ARPC5 (GFP)	Forward	<i>Bam</i> HI	GGATCCAATGGCAGAATTCGTTGAAGCTG
	Reverse	<i>Hind</i> III	AAGCTTCAAACGGTGTGATGGTATCAGTAAG
ARPC5 (mCh)	Forward	<i>Bam</i> HI	AAAGGATCCATGGCAGAATTCGTTGAAG
	Reverse	<i>Xma</i> I	TTTCCCGGGAACGGTGTGATGGTATCAG
MCD	Forward	<i>Bam</i> HI	AAAAAAGGATCCATGAGCAAGAAAAATCTAGCGATTC
	Reverse	<i>Eco</i> RI	AAAAAAGAATTCCTAGAGACGGGAATGGATAC